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LIFE-CYCLE ENGINEERING AND SUSTAINABILITY IN THE CLASSROOM: TACKLING THE ISSUE OF PLASTIC WASTE

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This workshop will focus on using data and tools for sustainability and lifecycle investigations in design and materials-related courses. It is important that material life-cycles are discussed in such courses, to encourage future generations of product developers to consider long-term effects. The specific problem that will be tackled in this workshop is the urgent issue of plastic waste and the case of PET water bottles. The Enhanced Eco Audit tool will be utilized as a means of developing critical thinking and awareness in product development and design.

The challenge of plastic waste accumulating in landfills, on beaches and in the sea has many dimensions – economic, social and environmental. Public campaigns, government initiatives, and global media coverage contribute to the growing awareness of this type of material life-cycle problem. Real-world concerns like this are a powerful way of engaging students on engineering and design courses, and encouraging them to consider the (sometimes unintended) consequences arising from materials decisions.

During the decision-making process, different materials need to be considered along with alternative concepts which minimize negative environmental (and social) impact. In a hands-on, practical group exercise that makes use of the Eco Audit tool, we show that CES EduPack can be used to aid discussion and help informed decision-making in product development. We provide a life-cycle investigation of PET bottles and some alternative water containers using the tool, and demonstrate a problem-based activity that can be directly used in your classroom together with the software. Workshop participants will also explore the Sustainability Database of CES EduPack to analyze and discuss broader environmental and socioeconomic issues related to material use.

In the workshop you will:

- Learn about a problem-based approach to assessing the sustainability of products and technological developments
- Gain practical knowledge and skills regarding eco-data and eco-informed materials selection in life-cycle engineering and eco design

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- Experience a practical and hands-on example of how to use the Eco Audit Tool to explore the issue of plastic waste
 - Find out about case studies, exercises, lecture units, and other teaching resources available for educators.

At the conclusion of the workshop, you should be able to:

- Confidently know how to use CES EduPack to teach students sustainability concepts
- Implement a problem-based system approach in your design or materials-related teaching
- Gain a practical example with templates and a fully developed case study to use in your teaching
- Get one-month access to the test license of CES EduPack to try out with your students.